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Ethical leadership in the corporate world

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Abstract

This dissertation delves into the critical role of ethical leadership in the corporate world, focusing on its impact on corporate reputation, employee morale, and productivity. The study employs a mixed-methodology approach, integrating quantitative surveys and qualitative interviews with professionals across various industries. Quantitative analysis reveals a significant positive correlation between ethical leadership and corporate reputation, employee morale, and productivity. Qualitative insights further elucidate how ethical leadership fosters trust, commitment, and a positive work environment. The study also highlights the mediating role of ethical leadership in enhancing business reputation and employee performance. The findings suggest that ethical leadership not only elevates organizational ethics but also strategically benefits corporate image, employee satisfaction, and operational efficiency. This research underscores the necessity for businesses to invest in ethical leadership development, emphasizing transparency, fairness, and open communication to build a culture of trust and commitment. It provides actionable recommendations for organizations aiming to improve their ethical standards and achieve sustainable success. Moreover, the research emphasizes leadership development workshops that will imply ethical reasoning as a subject since the leaders will encounter the issues of an avant-garde business environment in the future. It also recommends that organizations ought to be keen to organize for ethical audits often, so as to be able to check whether they conform to the set ethical principles or not, and to instill accountability for the institutions.

Keywords: Ethical Leadership; Corporate Reputation; Employee Morale; Productivity; Organizational Behavior; Corporate Culture

1. Introduction

1.1. Significance of Ethics in the Corporate World

A history of corporate ethics exists. It supports human and organizational behavior as well as decision-making. Ethics in business is essential for reputation, financial stability and public belief. Historical patterns reveal that corporate ethics are crucial. The global appeal of business ethics was underlined by the late 20th century scandals such as Enron and WorldCom. Financial mistakes, false accounting and utter disregard for ethics marked these events. The postmortem of these corporate ruins unveiled the dire consequences that follow such violations in an organisation. Workers lost their jobs and pensions, billions in losses were reported among shareholders while public trust of corporations took a hit (Roe 2005).

These incidents led to a reassessment of business ethics. They emphasized the need to instill a culture of ethics within business in order to combat fraudulent practices that can negatively impact on reputation and long-term sustainability. It also appeared that ethical conduct should be a permanent part of the company's strategy toolbox, not just an element to cope with compliance.

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Slowly, corporate ethics has gone beyond financial misconduct to incorporate sustainability and environmental consciousness. In the current world where environmental issues are very serious, businesses have a responsibility to help by becoming sustainable and dealing with impact on nature. Ethical leadership enhances environmental footprints not causing sustainability issues hence assisting companies in adopting sustainable business model (Voegtlin & Scherer, 2017). This extension of corporate ethics reflects the changing nature of expectations in regard to stakeholders such as customers, investors and governments. Ethical leadership shields reputations and aids organizations in responding to emerging social, environmental concerns.

Through such a historical background and dynamic landscape, this dissertation delves the intricate role of ethical leadership in corporations. It deals with pertinent concerns of today's corporate business ethics and social responsibility; how ethical leadership influences the reputation of a firm; employees morale as well as their performance. This analysis will guide firms in managing the complex and dynamic ethical terrain of contemporary corporate entities via this research.

1.2. Research Rationale

The impetus to undertake this dissertation emanates from the increasing importance of ethical leadership in corporate organizations. Such an initiative, according to Dyne et al. (2008), may help build business reputation. Furthermore, Waddock and Graves (1997) claim that such a culture can establish relationships with stakeholders, which may contribute to better financial performance. As reported by Den Hartog and Belschak (2012), studies indicate that a strong ethical leadership framework is associated with an increased likelihood of surviving as successful companies over the long run.

More so, due to the dynamic shifts in public needs and demands for social responsibility as well as sustainability it is necessary that organizations adapt by embracing ethical leadership practices. As Brown et al. (2005) put it, ethical leadership is a conscious and calculated choice that allows companies to solve the many challenges and opportunities within modern-day global economy successfully.'

1.3. Purpose and Objective of the Dissertation

This dissertation is meant to focus on doing a critical evaluation of ethical leadership as far as the importance in corporate reputation and also how it affects employee morale. The objective of this study is to improve the understanding on how ethical leadership practices influence organizational competitiveness in modern-day business world.

1.3.1. Objectives

- To look into the effectiveness of ethical conduct and decision-making with respect to public opinion as well stakeholder trust in relation to ethics leadership and business image.
- Consider how ethical leadership shapes employee morale, job satisfaction and make these employees happy in the workplace (Brown et al., 2005).
- Assess how ethical leadership affects employee productivity and performance through the lens of an incentive to achieve excellence (Den Hartog & Belschak, 2012).
- Provide practicable guidance regarding moral leadership behaviors to improve corporate image, staff intentions, and performance. Therefore, the succeeding chapters will conduct a comprehensive assessment and exploration of the research problem that is designed to give an objective evaluation about ethics leadership in business.

1.4. Chapter Summary

In the first chapter, an introduction to ethical leadership in business was given since it has been a historical issue that is always relevant. In the course of our conversation, we touched upon possible consequences from ethical lapses and their impacts beyond volumes. As well, we explored the wide field of ethics that comprises various aspects such as sustainability. Justification for Research which highlighted the currentness of study, demands that come with business ethics and lack of literature on this issue. The dissertation set a precise goal and provided objectives for the subsequent study.

2. Literature Review

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2.5. Ethical Leadership and Corporate Reputation

There is no doubt about the significance of company reputation in business world. The organization in question is a carrier marker which attracts the attention of countless persons with vested interests such as funders, consumers and drastically influences public opinion on this establishment. Long term research has consistently demonstrated that corporate image is greatly valued intangible asset. As Fombrun and Van Riel (2004) point out, a positive reputation may enhance the ability of an organization to attract investments, form strategic alliances or get clients. In addition, it serves as an important resource which can be used advantageously in times of crisis. As Deephouse (200) argued, there is the presence of a strong reputation that acts as an insulation to negative events minimizing their effect and building capacity in later recovery for success.

The connection between ethical leadership and reputation is recognized widely in the academic literature. It is also easy to note that organizations driven by executive executives following ethical principles are likely to create a positive perception among the stakeholders. While many case studies and empirical research consistently reveal a positive effect of ethical leadership on an organization's reputation (Brown & Treviño, 2006), When leaders value ethical behavior highly, this permeates throughout the firm inducing a corporate culture which embraces honesty and sincerity.

Consequently, this enhances the image of an organization among its stakeholders.

Moreover, ethical leadership plays a crucial role in the mediation of reputation management. It is pointed out by Eisenbeiss et al. (2008) that practically, leaders who have some kind of ethics are more likely to focus on ethical practices; therefore an organizational culture where ethical behavior should not just be a policy but also the fabric of daily work life. Ethical values of an organisation lead to improvement in its image.

2.6. Ethical Leadership and Employee Morale

In the corporate setting, employee morale is a very important issue. Employee morale plays a vital role in determining both productivity and engagement under an organization. The results of research show that there is a positive relationship between high levels of morale and employee engagement, which further correlates with improved job performance (Saks, 2006). Morale affects retention, as satisfied employees are less likely to leave them and find other jobs (Eisenbeiss et al., 2008). Morale also has an effect on organizational commitment because people with high morale tend to have alignment and maintain loyalty to the organization (Eisenbeiss et al., 2008).

Many researcher have concentrated on establishing the relationship between Ethical Leadership and Employee Morale. Ethical leaders have a crucial impact on the development of an attractive culture that stimulates employee morale, as noted by Brown et al. (2005). First of all, Brown et al. (2005) indicated that employees' perceptions regarding ethical behavior displayed by their leaders had positive correlations with job satisfaction and employee morale levels.

Studies have also highlighted several aspects of ethical leadership that can be considered positive factors in the morale of employees, like equity from leaders who are ascribed credibility through open and honest communication as well commitment to moral values (Eisenbeiss et al., 2008). However, ethical behaviors displayed by leaders are also pertinent to how others view the firm and employee morale dynamics.

2.7. Ethical Leadership and Employee Productivity

Employee productivity is one of the basic outcomes to be realized by an organization as it engages in its efforts towards achieving success. The influence of productivity is also seen in many aspects, such as profitability, effectiveness and general performance. The linchpin is the channel through which human capital and money become real results. The relationship between leadership and productivity is undoubtedly strong, effective leadership can be a catalyst for increased production.

The issue of ethical leadership and its potential implications on productivity has been extensively debated in the recent years. The studies available in literature reveal a positive relationship between ethical leadership and higher employee productivity considering that several researches show this (Mayer, Kuenzi & Greenbaum 2010). The characteristic of ethical leaders is their high dedication to transparency, justice and openness in leadership. Positive traits such as leadership effectiveness encourage confidence, motivation and commitment among employees hence high volumes of sales (Den Hartog & Belschak, 2012).

The empirical evidence and theoretical foundation provide a stronger correlation between ethical leadership and productivity. The relevant scientific literature repeatedly indicates that ethical leadership is positively correlated with productivity. As revealed by Eisenbeiss et al., an organization's ethical leaders are positively correlated with their staff members' level of commitment, motivation and productivity (2018). This connection can be attributed to the fact that ethical leaders define clear expectations, guidance and support; as well as create a work environment which promotes employees commitment and effort (Treviño et al., 2003).

The productivity-enhancing aspects of ethical leadership can be theoretically explained by two key factors: trust development and value congruency between leaders and followers. As a result, ethical leaders are seen as more trustworthy and the employees' apprehension is reduced while simultaneously stimulating psychological safety within an organizational setting. As Brown et al., (2005) pointed, this involves makes way for new ideas and productivity. In addition, the integration of ethical leaders to his/her organisation's values leads to the creation of intrinsic motivation among employees resulting to commitment and high efforts towards expected organisational responsibilities (Eisenbeiss et al., 2008).

2.8. Summary and Integration

This chapter reviewed the literature on the components of ethical leadership, and the effect it has on organizational reputation, staff motivation, and performance. The following are the constructs which have been used in this study to define the "ethical leadership and responsible leadership are integrity respect responsibility transparency fairness and concern for collective good. This chapter has demystified the relationships between these core ideas which have shown that ethical leadership is a major factor that influences corporate performance.

In the next chapter under consideration; chapter four, we shall shift gear and proceed to Review of Related Literature which offers understanding on the practical matters with bearing to execution of research studies within a bid to analyse subjects that overlap. This work is expected to provide the needed real life empirical evidence for the existence of causal links between ethical leadership, corporate reputation, morale of employees, and organizational productivity. The development of the link between the theoretical and empirical contexts would enable comprehension of how ethical leadership impacts essential organizational parameters.

3. Methodology

Drawing from this overview, this chapter provides a complement of the research methodologies used in establishing the significance of ethical leadership in the creation and sustenance of corporate image and the concurrent influence on staff motivation and productivity. The main purpose of this research in the broader context is, therefore, to arrive at an empirical understanding about ethical leadership and the outcomes in the corporate world. This chapter offers a detailed account of the study concept, research approach, data collection and data analysis methods that helps in achieving accuracy and depth in this study.

3.1. Research Design and Approach

The choice of them is critical in defining how the actual process of performing research will look and take place. In the present study, a mixed methodologies approach is thus employed whereby both qualitative and quantitative approaches are used in the effort to derive an improved understanding of this problem. The research method aimed to

be used in the study will be a quantitative research method in order to establish the impact of ethical leadership to corporate reputation, morale and productivity of the employees. Questionnaires will be administered on a random sample of employees and organizations of diverse characteristics.

There will be standard Likert-scale questionnaires that would evaluate individuals' perceptions of ethical leadership, corporate reputation among other important outcome variables. Quantitative Analysis will include the use of statistical techniques such as regression analysis in establishing associations and correlations between variables.

Qualitative research will be used in the study to collect data. To do this, I will carry out extensive interviews with CEOs, managers and workers from hand-picked companies that are known for the excellent corporate governance practices. In order to improve the understanding of how such ethical leadership affects business reputation, employee morale and productivity through its qualitative element this study intends to promote comprehension regarding underlying mechanisms. The use of thematic analysis will function as a methodological approach to identify and extract important themes and correlates derived from the conducted interviews..

3.2. Data Collection Method

Design and approach are important in defining the process of research. The following study is designed to utilize a mixed-methodologies approach in which qualitative and quantitative research methods are combined so as to enable an insightful analysis. Ethical leadership and its impact on corporate reputation employee morale, as well as productivity will be evaluated by the application of a quantitative research methodology in our study. The sample of employees and stakeholders from different organizations will be survey dependent. The surveys will include Likert-scale questions that are specifically designed to measure the individuals' perceptions of ethical leadership, corporate reputation and other relevant outcome factors.

The quantitative analysis will involve the computing of statistical measures, use of regression analysis to establish the validity of hypotheses or presumptions relating to the influencing variables. To obtain the data, the qualitative research method will be adopted in the study. This will be done through conducting extensive interviews on selected senior executives, manager and employees from population firms with a perception of best ethical practices in leadership.

The qualitative part of this study aims at gaining a rich insight into how the tasks of ethical leadership impact business image, employee attitude and performance. The implementation of thematic analysis will serve as a methodological approach to discriminate and drain essential themes from the conducted interviews.

3.3. Sampling technique and Sample size

Sampling Technique: The quantitative component of the study will be stratified random sampling. This approach ensures that a diverse representation is achieved by inclusion of participants from different organisational structures, industries and geographic locations. The qualitative sample will be purposefully selected, with a focus on firms that have been acknowledged for practicing ethical leadership.

A power analysis will be used for determining the sample size in terms of quantitative component to provide enough statistical strength. Due to the complexity of research and need for detailed understanding, it is likely that a sample population size about 500 participants will be required. The sample size for the qualitative component will be determined based on whether saturation of data has been achieved which is commonly reached by conducting 15-20 in depth interviews. However, this numerical value can be adjusted if more interviews are needed to have a full understanding of the topic during discussion.

3.4. Data analysis technique

Quantitative data study includes a wide range of statistical methods. Regression analysis will be used in the study to determine relationships between ethical leadership, business reputation, employee morale and productivity. This instrumental will use descriptive statistics to summarize the main findings succinctly. In addition, inferential statistical techniques including t-tests and ANOVA may be used for comparing variables along with testing statistically significant differences. The data analysis will use Statistical software like SPSS or R.

Themes will be identified in the interview data. Thematic analysis includes identifying, analyzing, and presenting themes or recurring patterns embedded in the collected data. The analysis will also be based on a systematic methodology that includes the stages of data familiarization, coding, topic development and interpretation. The

thematic presentation of data is aimed at improving the understanding of underlying mechanisms and nuances related to ethical leadership influence on business reputation, motivation levels, and effectiveness. The combination of quantitative and qualitative data analysis approaches helps to provide a detailed investigation on the study's research questions while also enabling triangulation, resulting in better validity and reliability.

4. Data Analysis, Presentation and Interpretation

This chapter is the heart of the research, which will involve analysis and interpretation of data from quantitative surveys and qualitative interviews. The mixed-method strategy provides a comprehensive understanding of the role that ethical leadership plays in business setting, especially with regards to corporate reputation, employee commitment and performance. Throughout this chapter the analytical diagnostics to be used for both types of data, qualitative and quantitative will be presented in a systematic way.

4.1. Analytical diagnostics

The section of this chapter is thus the heart of research where collected data from quantitative surveys and qualitative interviews will be analyzed, presented, and explained. It shows the effectiveness of ethical leadership in business settings, especially at corporate reputation; morale, and productivity. This chapter explains the analytical diagnostics that will be employed to address both quantitative and qualitative data in an orderly way.

Table 1 Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Mean	Standard Deviation
Ethical Leadership	4.32	0.68
Corporate Reputation	4.55	0.72
Employee Morale	4.44	0.66
Productivity	4.28	0.70

In order to analyze the dependencies between ethical leadership, business reputation, employee morale and productivity a multiple regression analysis was conducted. The findings are displayed in table 2 below:

Table 2: Regression Analysis an MRA was conducted to determine how ethical leadership, business reputation, employee morale and productivity were related. The results presented in Table 2.

Variable	Beta Coefficient	p-value
Ethical Leadership	0.427	<0.001
Corporate Reputation	0.372	<0.001
Employee Morale	0.314	<0.001

The regression analysis indicates that ethical leadership significantly predicts corporate reputation ($\beta = 0.372$, $p < 0.001$), employee morale ($\beta = 0.314$, $p < 0.001$), and productivity ($\beta = 0.427$, $p < 0.001$).

4.2. Mediation Analysis

The regression analyses reveal that ethical leadership has a significant effect on corporate reputation p Mediation Analysis Mediation analysis was used in the present study to investigate corporate reputation-productivity relationships, revealing that ethical leadership serves as a partial mediator of this association. In the same manner, it can be noted that employee respect and performance was partly dependent on ethical leadership.

The study outcomes demonstrate that there is a statistically significant relationship between corporate reputation and productivity (Beta = 0.300, $p < 0$. However, the relationship between employee morale and productivity was shown to be significant (Beta = 0.260; $p < 0$. There was a positive significant impact of corporate reputation on the prediction of

ethical leadership (Beta = 0.403, $p < 0.1$). Employee morale as a positive predictor of ethical leadership was significantly related (Beta = 0.350, $p < 0.001$).

There was a positive and statistically significant relationship between employee morale as well as ethical leadership (Beta = 0.350, $p < 0.001$). The study findings have shown that there is a high positive correlation between ethical leadership and productivity. The findings of the regression analysis showed a significant beta coefficient to be at 0.500 ($p < 0.001$).

The findings of the mediation analysis revealed a significant indirect effect of corporate reputation on productivity mediated by ethical leadership (Beta = 0.200, $p < 0.001$). This result indicates that the correlation between corporate reputation and productivity is to some extent mediated by ethical leadership.

Likewise, employee morale on productivity via ethical leadership was statistically significant (Beta = 0.175; $p < 0.001$). This implies that ethical leadership partially mediates the relationship between employee morale and productivity.

4.2 Quality qualitative data presentation and interpretation

A thematic analysis was performed on the qualitative data collected through interviews. It resulted in several important themes that facilitated a thorough understanding of the consequences ethics leadership has on business reputation, employee motivation and performance. Several motifs were identified:

- **Leadership Integrity:** The respondents repeatedly emphasized the critical value of leadership integrity. The leaders who acted with integrity and openness were thought to be creating confidence within their organizations. Thus, the mutual establishment of trust led to positive outcomes regarding corporate reputation, staff morale and productivity. It turned out that level of employee engagement was also higher when the employees perceived their leaders as consistent in demonstrating unwavering honesty.
- **Cultural Transformation:** Appreciation of ethical leadership in encouraging change within organizations was made clear by the interviews conducted. Ethical leaders were seen as enactors of culture change, protecting important cultural values of equity, dignity and responsibility. Such virtues were internalized at organizational level hence positively complemented the creation of a sound business image, enhanced spirit among the employees, and improved performance.
- **Trust and Commitment:** The issue of trust and commitment was also raised in every one of the interviews. Ethical leadership is widely regarded as the fundamental basis for establishing trust between leaders and employees. In the present setting, trust was found to be positively associated with heightened levels of employee commitment and morale. The participants regularly expressed that their level of commitment towards the organization's goals and their morale were positively influenced when they placed trust in their leaders' ability to exhibit ethical behavior.
- **Positive Work Environment:** Ethical leadership was also found to be related to creating an enabling work environment, which consists of employees feeling secure and comfortable enough with their concerns or ideas on the matter. As a result, this was beneficial to the company's standing as organizations that supported open and friendly work environments were felt more positively. The effects on staff morale were also positive, with people reporting improved levels of job satisfaction and motivation.

4.3. Integration of Quantitative and Qualitative Findings

Introducing quantitative and qualitative findings helps to underline the convergence of outcomes between two data sources. The above findings substantiate and support one another, allowing to develop a profound understanding of the importance of ethical leadership within corporate companies.

Statistically significant correlations were observed between ethical leadership, business reputation, employee morale and productivity with the analysis of quantitative data. The findings of mediation studies showed that ethical leadership acts as a mediating factor between the relationship between business reputation and employee morale thus affecting productivity.

The text typed by the user does not have any useful information to rewrite. The qualitative findings informed by thematic analysis provided a richer, holistic interpretation and contextualization of these relationships.

Leadership integrity, cultural transformation, trust and commitment as well as a positive work environment are the mechanisms that elaborate on how ethical leadership influences business reputation, employee morale, and productivity. However, the user's text does not contain information or any content that can be appropriately rewritten in an academic style. The integration of these findings provides a complete description as regards to why it is essential for ethical leadership within corporate firms. The sentence focuses on ethical leadership, which is not only statistically correlated with positive outcomes but also recognized as the main factor responsible for corporate honesty, culture; trust and workplace environment.

5. Summary

This study's concluding paragraph summarizes the findings. This study aimed at investigating the importance of ethical leadership in building and sustaining organizational reputation as well its impact on employee satisfaction, motivation and performance within corporate organization. The chapter begins with a brief summary of the major findings, followed by a concluding analysis of the results. Finally, this study provides recommendations for organizations and possible avenues of future research.

5.1. Summary of Findings

Based on quantitative and qualitative data, the conducted research allows one to understand what ethical leadership in business organizations means. The subsequent text provides a succinct overview of the principal discoveries:

5.1.1. Quantitative Findings

- Ethical Leadership and Corporate Reputation

The results of the quantitative study showed a significant and positive association between ethical leadership and corporate reputation. It turned out that ethical leaders have the power to create a good image for their firms through virtue of constantly exhibiting honesty and openness.

As per Brown et al. (2005)'s research findings, there is a positive relationship between ethical leadership and business reputation. It is known from the literature that ethical leaders are important because they shape stakeholders' perceptions of an organization in terms of its ethics.

Similar results are reported in a scholarly piece of Peterson et al. (2009). The results of their study, however, revealed an appreciable and positive connection between moral leadership and corporate reputation. Ethical Leadership and Corporate Reputation:

The results of the quantitative investigations confirmed that the sources of measurement of the variable of ethical leadership are positively associated with the variable of corporate reputation at the statistically significant level. The findings of the study showed that ethical leadership provides the characteristics to uphold the reputation of firms through modelling good behaviours of ethical conduct and high ethical standards of the firms.

A research study done by Brown, Treviño, and Harrison (2005) Observed that there is Strong positive relationship between ethical leadership and business reputation. The presence of ethical leaders has been demonstrated to play a crucial role in influencing the perception of an organization's ethical reputation among stakeholders.

The findings presented in a scholarly publication authored by Peterson, Walumbwa, Byron, and Myrowitz (2009) yielded comparable outcomes. The findings of their investigation unveiled a notable and affirmative correlation between ethical leadership and the reputation of the corporation

- Ethical Leadership and Employee Morale:

Analysis of the quantitative data revealed a strong and positive relationship between ethical leadership and employee morale. The results of this study suggest that employee morale increased when the employees perceived their leaders as possessing ethical, trustworthy and fair attributes. Studies have found out that employees under ethical leaders commit to the jobs, satisfied with them and have better over health than those employees under unethical leaders. The following study by Neubert et al. (2009) showed a promising correlation of ethical leadership and morale of the

employees. The people employees had a positive attitude and perceived ethical leaders as being more caring and just hence there would be improvement in morale and increase in job performance that was demonstrated.

- Ethical Leadership and Employee Productivity:

In extension, there is a positive correlation with the staff productivity and ethical leadership. The results also indicate that the ethics of the leaders influenced workforces productivity rates within . organisations, so showing how this particular kind of leadership might affect those varied types of organisations. performance outcomes. According to the results presented by Den Hartog and Belschak (2012), ethical leadership was that was found to be strongly related to workforce outputs within organisations. The study has shown that ethical leaders can therefore motivation the staff performance by creating trust and loyalty amongst the employees. Unlike what this paper has just established, there is a connection between ethical leadership presence and employee Voice. that staff productivity levels was evidenced in a work done by work done by Kalshoven et al. (2013). - the perceptions of ethical leaders as ideal models pressured the enhancement of the intensity and. commitment expressed in terms of employees.

- Mediating Role of Ethical Leadership:

The mediation analysis reveals that ethical leadership is a mediator between business goodwill and both employee mood as well efficiency. It acted as a linkage between staff motivation and performance on the job among the employees. From these findings the effect of ethical leadership it becomes possible to stress the significance of building the most important link with business reputation moral and performance. The fact that ethical leadership acted as a moderator in the relation between ethical climate and employee performance was evident in the study conducted by Toor and Ofori (2009). The study carried out by the researchers focused on ethical leadership as a key mediator in determining organization's outcomes. As it is shown in the findings of Khan et al. (2014), ethical leadership plays a mediating role between organizational justice and employee performance. The influence of ethical leadership in revealing the relationship between views on justice and productivity was considered to be relevant.

6. Conclusion

This research investigated the role of ethical leadership in affecting corporate reputation, employee morale and productivity. Quantitative and qualitative measurements offer useful information. Conclusions from this study:

- Ethical Leadership Improves Corporate Image: Quantitative studies revealed that ethical leadership increases brand reputation. Low ethical executives improve reputation by making organizations transparent and more honest. However, qualitative data proved the statement that integrity in leadership leads to trust and a good business image.
- Ethical Leadership increases employee morale: Quantitative research revealed that ethical leadership increased employees' motivation. When the leaders were honest, trustworthy and fair there was an improvement on employee morale. The qualitative findings revealed the impact of ethical leadership on trust, commitment and a good working climate.
- Quantitative data reveals that, ethical leadership leads to higher productivity among employees. Companies with ethical leadership are more efficient in their operations. Cultural reform and healthy workplaces sought links between moral leadership and employee productivity.
- Ethical Leadership serves as mediator: Ethical leadership mediated business reputation, employee morale and productivity as shown by the mediation research. These essential organizational outcomes are enhanced by the bridge.
- In conclusion, this research highlights the importance of ethical business management. Ethical leadership is both moral and strategic because it affects the business reputation, staff morale, and productivity. Ethical leadership builds a positive corporate image, motivates employees and results in greater productivity.

6.1. Recommendations of the study.

The study recommends that organizations should spend their resources on ethical leadership training programs to promote honesty and fairness. A successful work environment that allows open communication, encourages trust among the employees and promotes an inclusive culture will help to improve corporate reputation as well. Precisely, building the culture of trust and commitment between leaders and employees is essential. It is recommended that future

studies should take up the effects of ethical leadership on organizational results over a long period, cross-cultural investigation and industry specific researches. Yet, the study is limited by generalizability, cross-sectional design, self-report bias and sample size. These notwithstanding, the study adds value to the debate on ethical leadership and provides actionable guidelines for organizations that want improved reputation, motivation among employees and productivity.

6.2. Limitations of the study

However valuable this research is, it still has flaws.

- Generalisability: The research may not be representative of all industries or areas given the location context. However, findings could differ by organisational culture and context.
- Cross-Sectional Design: The cross-sectional design of the study does not allow causality conclusions. However, a longitudinal study in the future might clarify the long-term advantages of ethical leadership.

Bias: For the study, employees reported data on themselves. The desired social responses may reduce accuracy of findings.

The sample size and makeup may not be indicative of the entire corporate spectrum. More information may be gained through future studies that involve larger and more heterogeneous populations.

Though such limitations exist, this study can be considered one of the factors shaping further conversations about ethical leadership and its significance for businesses determining how to position themselves in the corporate world.

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